

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO ASSESSING TALENTED STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE THROUGH TEST TASKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10802244>

Abstract. *Method of determining the knowledge of talented students through test assignments is given and methods of solving physics test tasks are presented.*

Keywords: *test, olympiad, cognitive, didactics, innovation, mass, pressure, horizontal, corner .*

Introduction

The main task of teachers and coaches is to educate the young generation as independent-minded, truly patriotic people with modern knowledge and skills, with a healthy life position. The current development of science and technology requires the training of more highly qualified specialists in the natural and technical fields. In designing the processes of preparing physics students for higher educational institutions, competitions and Olympiads, the correct definition of educational content, educational goals, expected results, and the correct selection of educational methods, forms and tools, it is desirable to develop specific criteria for assessing students' knowledge, skills and qualifications in advance, to pay attention to the implementation of training and their coordination with each other. The importance of innovative approaches in evaluating students' acquired knowledge through test tasks is very great. First, let's pay attention to the meaning of the word innovation. Lexically, the concept of "innovation" when translated from the English language ("innovation") means "introducing something new". Innovation is an activity aimed at changing the internal structure of a particular system. Educational innovations consist of forms, methods and technologies that are used to solve existing problems in the field of education or the educational process based on a new approach, which are more effective than the previous ones. Educational innovations are also known as innovative education.

Solving Test assignments provides opportunities for students with sufficient knowledge of physics to consolidate their knowledge as well as to form practice skills. One of the most important practical techniques in teaching physics is the solution of test assignments. Solving assignments plays an important role in teaching students to practical application of the knowledge and skills they have acquired.

Methods

Recent years, in Uzbekistan, the method of checking the students' knowledge through test materials remains one of the popular methods. The Test is a test tool that allows you to set a certain state level in qualitative and quantitative indicators based on a specific goal. Test assignments are structured in such a way that each of them, as a rule, checks the knowledge of the subject or section of the program. A total of 30 test assignments are recommended to test students knowledge in the group. In this case, the first 10 tests consist of theoretical questions about the nature of the subject, our daily lifestyle, technology and life activities, the next 10 tests check how much they memorize formulas, graphs and units on the topic, The Last 10 tests consist of tests on the calculation on the topic and check the mathematical literacy of students. Answering a relatively large number of such kind of questions is such that a number of answers are offered to each of them, from which the

reader is required to choose one correct answer. Test assignments check the following private competencies occupied by students in a theoretical way: observing, understanding and explaining the physical process and phenomena; measuring and determining physical magnitudes; conducting experiments and drawing conclusions, and being able to use physical knowledge and instruments in practice. The Test includes the following assessment goals to determine whether students have acquired cognitive skills:

1) cognitive skills of knowing and understanding, in which students know concepts, terms, physical magnitudes and their units, laws and link formulas related to physical phenomena;

2) applied cognitive skill, in which students can write the interweaving of physical magnitudes in the form of mathematical expressions, draw conclusions and;

3) Analyzing cognitive skills in which students can complete and evaluate tests that require extended and creative reasoning related to molecular physics and thermodynamics[P.1, 64].

Olympic tests in physics include a problematic situation and elements of novelty. Special time for solving Olympic test tasks in physics and individual lessons on solving tests, courses, optional lessons will be held. Educational tools perform the following didactic functions: to explain the materials and phenomena studied by reading, to increase the possibilities of reading and studying physical phenomena, based on the principle of operation of physical instruments and devices, to clearly demonstrate the mechanism of occurrence of phenomena, to prove various physical phenomena, connections in experience that they are in a causal relationship. Students are advised to use an algorithmic method to solve physics test assignments[4].

Below we recommend methodologies for solving test tasks from physics:

3. The lower end, located in a vertical position, is separated from the outer atmosphere by Mercury of h height, the air inside the soldered tube. Find the air pressure at the bottom of the mercury if the upper end of the tube is open and the atmospheric pressure is p_0 . ρ is the density of mercury. g – free fall acceleration.

A) $p_0 + \rho gh$ B) $p_0 - \rho gh$ C) $p_0 + \frac{1}{2} \rho gh$ D) p_0

Given: h, p_0, ρ, g . $h = 3m$. Need to find: $p = ?$

Solution: As described in the figure 1, we write the equilibrium state of the strengths acting on the h – height mercury: $pS = p_0S + mg$ from which we find the pressure p : $p = p_0 + \frac{mg}{S}$

Figure 1

The mass of mercury at height h is equal to: $m = \rho Sh$. We put this in the formula of the pressure above: $p = p_0 + \frac{\rho Shg}{S} = p_0 + \rho gh$. Answer: $p = p_0 + \rho gh$

It is recommended that the teacher change the position of the tube to 180^0 or make new test assignments by placing the tube at some angle with the horizon.

2. The height of the hermetically closed container is 3m, and it is drained with water. Two identical air bubbles stand at the bottom of the container. The pressure at the base of the vessel is 0,15 MPa. What will be the pressure in the base if one bubble pops up ? [2, 167 p]

- A) $\approx 0,17MPa$ B) $\approx 0,32MPa$ C) $\approx 0,43MPa$ D) $\approx 0,67MPa$

Given : $h = 3m$, $\rho = 1000kg / m^3$, $p = 0,15Mpa$. Need to find: $p_1 = ?$ $p_2 = ?$

The volume increases if one bubble comes up. We mark it with V_2 . Let's set the size of the remaining bubble to the base of the container with V_1 . Then we can write the following from the ideal gas state equation for both bubbles:

$$pV_0 = p_1V_1 \quad (1) \qquad pV_0 = p_1^1V_2 \quad (2)$$

Figure 2

From the equilibrium condition of the forces we have: $p_1S = mg + p_1^1S$ here, $m = \rho V = \rho Sh$ - water mass in the container, S - the base surface of the cylinder. $p_1 = \rho gh + p_1^1$. Then the pressure at the top of the container: $p_1^1 = p_1 - \rho gh$, putting this into Equation (2) we have:

$$pV_0 = (p_1 - \rho gh)V_2 \quad (3)$$

The liquid is not compressed so the total volume of bubbles is maintained:

$$V_1 + V_2 = 2V_0 \quad (4)$$

From (1) and (3) we find V_1 and V_2 and put (4) we get:

$$\frac{pV_0}{p_1} + \frac{pV_0}{p_1 - \rho gh} = 2V_0$$

From this quadratic equation, p_1 is found: $p_1 = 0,1665MPa \approx 0,17MPa$ and $p_1 = 0,0135MPa$ - since this pressure is very small, we do not take it into account.

Answer: $p_1 = 0,1665MPa \approx 0,17MPa$

Conclusion

We believe that the tests obtained in physics are useful for students to be able to draw logical conclusions about the physical processes of nature that occur in everyday lifestyles, prepare for higher education institutions, prepare for olympiads.

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